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Version 1

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This analysis pipeline is partly based on an analysis workflow developed by Bernd Klaus.

R setup

Defining a working directory

We defined the working directory for the analysis. This directory should contain the metadata file and the tab delimited text files containing the data.

```
setwd("~/home/path to the right file location")
```

Loading packages

```
library(vsn)
library(limma)
library(MSNbase)
library(gplots)
library(fdrtool)
library(biobroom)
library(tidyverse)
```

Defining some functions and parameters

```
customPlot <- list(
  theme_bw(base_size = 12),
  scale_shape_manual(values = c(16, 17, 15, 3, 7, 8)),
  scale_fill_brewer(palette = "Set1"),
  scale_colour_brewer(palette = "Set1")
)
script.version <- "V1"
dir_save <- paste0("data_analysis_results_", script.version)
if (!dir.exists(dir_save))
{
  dir.create(dir_save)
}
```

Loading data and annotating experimental conditions

```
conditions <- read.delim("metadata.csv", sep = ";")
files <- file.path(unique(conditions$file))
files <- files[file.exists(files)]
data <- NULL
for (i in seq_along(files))
{
  print(files[i])
  x <- read_delim(file.path(files[i]), delim = " ")
  names(x) <- make.names(names(x))
  x$Gene[is.na(x$Gene)] <- x$Protein.ID[is.na(x$Gene)]
  #keep only proteins with at least two unique peptide matches
  x <- x %>%
    dplyr::filter(Unique.Peptides >= 2)
  #remove reverse hits
  x <- x %>%
    dplyr::filter(!grepl("rev_", Protein))
  #remove known contaminants
  x <- x %>%
    dplyr::filter(!grepl("contam_", Protein))
  x$file <- files[i]
  keepnames <- as.character(subset(conditions, file == files[i])$col.name)
  x <- x[, c("Gene", "Protein.ID", "Protein.Description", "Organism", "Unique.Peptides", "Total.Intensity")]
  x <- x %>%
    group_by(Gene, Protein.ID, Protein.Description, Organism, Unique.Peptides, Total.Intensity, file) %>%
    gather(key = "col.name", value = "value", keepnames)
  x$Total.Intensity <- as.numeric(as.character(x$Total.Intensity))
  data <- bind_rows(data, x)
  rm(x, keepnames)
}
```

```
## [1] "03_fractionated_OH_protein.tsv"
```

```
rm(i, files)
data <- left_join(data, conditions)
data <- subset(data, value > 0)
```

Protein identification overview

```
sub <- unique(data[, c("Gene", "file", "rep")])
sub$found <- 1
sub$file_old <- sub$file
sub$file <- paste("file", as.numeric(factor(sub$file)))
print(unique(with(sub, paste(file, "-", file_old))))
```

```
## [1] "file 1 - 03_fractionated_OH_protein.tsv"
```

```
sub$file_old <- NULL
sub <- unique(sub)
ggplot(data = sub, aes(file, fill = rep)) +
  geom_bar(position = position_dodge()) +
  customPlot +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1, vjust = 1))
```



```
with(sub, table(file, rep))
```

```
##      rep
## file  rep1 rep2 rep3
## file 1  742  742  742
```

```
sub_i <- data %>%
  group_by(Gene) %>%
  dplyr::select(Gene, rep, file) %>%
  unique() %>%
  summarise(found.in.files = n())
ggplot(data = sub_i, aes(found.in.files)) +
  geom_bar(position = position_dodge()) +
  customPlot +
  xlab("no of identifications per file")
```



```
table(sub_i$found.in.files)
```

```
##
## 3
## 742
```

```
rm(sub_i)
rm(sub)
```

Identification and removal of duplicated gene names

```
dup.data <- data %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  dplyr::select(Gene, Protein.ID, file, Unique.Peptides) %>%
  unique() %>%
  group_by(file, Gene) %>%
  dplyr::filter(n() > 1)
if (nrow(dup.data) > 0)
{
  write.csv(dup.data, file.path(dir_save, paste0("Duplicates_", script.version, ".csv")), row.names = F)
}
dups <- unique(dup.data$Gene)
if (length(dups) > 0)
{
  print("Duplicates were identified:")
  print(dups)
```

```

print("Removing genes with smaller numbers of quantified peptides.")
for (dup in dups)
{
  for (file in unique(subset(dup.data, Gene == dup)$file))
  {
    sub <- subset(data, Gene == dup & file == file)
    data <- subset(data, paste(Gene, file) != paste(dup, file))
    sub <- subset(sub, Unique.Peptides == max(sub$Unique.Peptides, na.rm = TRUE))
    data <- bind_rows(data, sub)
    rm(sub)
  }
  rm(file)
}
rm(dup)
}
dup.data <- data %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  dplyr::select(Gene, Protein.ID, file, Unique.Peptides) %>%
  unique() %>%
  group_by(file, Gene) %>%
  dplyr::filter(n() > 1)
dups <- unique(dup.data$Gene)
if (length(dups) > 0)
{
  print("Duplicates:")
  print(dups)
  print("Removing genes with the least overlap of protein ids in other ms experiments")
  for (dup in dups)
  {
    sub <- subset(data, Gene %in% dup)
    IDs <- unlist(strsplit(sub$Protein.ID, split = "[|]"))
    rm(sub)
    for (file in unique(subset(dup.data, Gene == dup)$file))
    {
      sub <- subset(data, Gene == dup & file == file)
      data <- subset(data, paste(Gene, file) != paste(dup, file))
      sub$ID.count <- 0
      for (ID in unique(sub$Protein.ID))
      {
        sub$ID.count[sub$Protein.ID == ID] <- length(which(IDs %in% unlist(strsplit(ID, split = "[|]"))))
      }
      sub <- subset(sub, ID.count == max(sub$ID.count, na.rm = TRUE))
      sub$ID.count <- NULL
      data <- bind_rows(data, sub)
      rm(sub)
    }
    rm(file, IDs)
  }
  rm(dup)
}
rm(dups, dup.data)

```

Transforming long data to wide data

```
ggplot(data = data, aes(condition, log2(value), fill = rep)) +  
  geom_boxplot() +  
  ylab("log2(signal_sum)") +  
  customPlot +  
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1, vjust = 1))
```



```
cdata <- data %>%  
  group_by(Gene) %>%  
  mutate(key = paste("signal_sum", condition, rep, sep = "_")) %>%  
  dplyr::select(Gene, key, value) %>%  
  group_by(Gene, key) %>%  
  summarise(value = sum(value, na.rm = TRUE)) %>%  
  spread(key = key, value = value)  
  
#found.in.files  
fdata <- data %>%  
  group_by(Gene) %>%  
  dplyr::select(Gene, file) %>%  
  unique() %>%  
  summarise(found.in.files = n())  
  
fdata_i <- data %>%  
  mutate(file2 = make.names(file)) %>%
```

```

group_by(Gene, file2) %>%
dplyr::select(Gene, file, file2) %>%
unique() %>%
summarise(found.in.file = n()) %>%
mutate(file2 = paste0("found.in.file_", file2)) %>%
spread(key = file2, value = found.in.file)
fdata <- left_join(fdata, fdata_i)
#found.in.conditions
fdata_i <- data %>%
group_by(Gene) %>%
dplyr::select(Gene, condition) %>%
unique() %>%
summarise(found.in.conditions = n())
fdata <- left_join(fdata, fdata_i)
#found.in.reps
fdata_i <- data %>%
group_by(Gene) %>%
dplyr::select(Gene, rep) %>%
unique() %>%
summarise(found.in.reps = n())
fdata <- left_join(fdata, fdata_i)
#Unique.Peptides overview
fdata_i <- data %>%
group_by(Gene) %>%
dplyr::select(Gene, Unique.Peptides) %>%
unique() %>%
summarise(max.Unique.Peptides = max(Unique.Peptides, na.rm = TRUE))
fdata <- left_join(fdata, fdata_i)
#abundance overview
fdata_i <- data %>%
group_by(Gene) %>%
dplyr::select(Gene, Total.Intensity) %>%
unique() %>%
summarise(average.Total.Intensity = mean(Total.Intensity, na.rm = TRUE))
fdata <- left_join(fdata, fdata_i)
id_data <- data %>%
ungroup() %>%
dplyr::select(Gene, Protein.ID, Protein.Description, Organism) %>%
unique()
dups <- id_data %>%
group_by(Gene) %>%
summarize(n = n()) %>%
dplyr::filter(n > 1) %>%
dplyr::select(Gene)
if (nrow(dups) > 0)
{
dups <- dups$Gene
dup.data <- subset(id_data, Gene %in% dups)
id_data <- subset(id_data, !Gene %in% dups)
combine_ids <- function(ids)
{
ids <- as.character(ids)
return(paste(

```

```

    sort(unique(unlist(strsplit(ids, split = "[{Fasta.name.split.char}]"))), collapse = "{Fasta.name
}
dup.data <- dup.data %>%
  group_by(Gene) %>%
  summarise(Protein.ID = combine_ids(Protein.ID),
            Protein.Description = combine_ids(Protein.Description),
            Organism = combine_ids(Organism))
id_data <- bind_rows(id_data, dup.data)
rm(dup.data, combine_ids)
}
rm(dups)
fdata <- left_join(id_data, fdata)
rm(id_data)
cdata <- left_join(fdata, cdata)
rm(fdata_i, fdata)

```

Filter data

Only proteins that were quantified with two unique peptide matches are kept for the analysis. Proteins were filtered according to these condition already when loading the data. Moreover, only proteins were kept if they were quantified in at least 2/3 of the replicates.

```

dim(cdata)

## [1] 742 28

min.found.in.files <- 1
min.Unique.Peptides <- 2
cdata <- cdata %>%
  dplyr::filter(found.in.files >= min.found.in.files, max.Unique.Peptides >= min.Unique.Peptides)
dim(cdata)

## [1] 742 28

rm(min.found.in.files, min.Unique.Peptides)

```

Building an expression set object

```

# Constructing assay data
raw_data <- cdata %>%
  dplyr::select(starts_with("signal_sum")) %>%
  as.data.frame()
rownames(raw_data) <- cdata$Gene
names(raw_data) <- gsub("signal_sum_", "", names(raw_data))

# Constructing metadata
conditions_i <- data.frame(ID = names(raw_data))
conditions_i <- left_join(conditions_i, conditions)

# Constructing fdata
fdata <- cdata %>%
  dplyr::select(-starts_with("signal_sum")) %>%
  as.data.frame()

```

```

# Defining ID columns
rownames(fdata) <- fdata$Gene
rownames(conditions_i) <- conditions_i$ID
colnames(raw_data) <- conditions_i$ID

# Log2-transformation of raw_signal_sums
raw_data_m <- log2(as.matrix(raw_data))
raw_data_m[is.infinite((raw_data_m))] <- NA
raw_data_m[is.na((raw_data_m))] <- NA

# Creating an expression set
raw_dataE <- ExpressionSet(assayData = raw_data_m,
                          phenoData = AnnotatedDataFrame(conditions_i),
                          featureData = AnnotatedDataFrame(fdata))
validObject(raw_dataE)

## [1] TRUE

rm(raw_data, raw_data_m, conditions_i, fdata)

```

Batch effect removal

```

batchcl_dataE <- raw_dataE
exprs(batchcl_dataE) <- removeBatchEffect(exprs(batchcl_dataE),
    batch = as.character(pData(batchcl_dataE)$rep),
    design = model.matrix(~0 + as.character(pData(batchcl_dataE)$condition)))

```

Data normalization

The vsn package from Wolfgang Huber is used to apply a variance stabilization normalization method on the log2 raw data.

```

norm_dataE <- batchcl_dataE
vsn.fit <- vsn2(2^exprs(batchcl_dataE))
meanSdPlot(vsn.fit)

```



```
norm_dataE <- batchcl_dataE
exprs(norm_dataE) <- predict(vsn.fit, 2^exprs(norm_dataE))

rm(sdplot.object, vsn.fit)
```

Calculation of ctrl-fold changes

```
fc.data <- as.data.frame(2^exprs(norm_dataE))
names.orig <- names(fc.data)
for (i in seq_along(conditions$ID))
{
  fc.data[, paste0(conditions$ID[i], ".ctrl.ratio")] <-
    fc.data[, as.character(conditions$ID[i])] /
    apply(fc.data[, grep(paste0("^", gsub("_[A-Z,a-z,0-9]+$", "_rep", conditions$ctrl.ID[i])), names.orig),
          # fc.data[, as.character(conditions$ctrl.ID[i])]
    )
}
rm(i)
fc.data <- fc.data %>%
  dplyr::select(ends_with(".ctrl.ratio"))
fc.data$Gene <- rownames(fc.data)
fc.data <- fc.data %>%
  dplyr::select(ends_with(".ctrl.ratio"))
ctrl.ratio_dataE <- norm_dataE
names(fc.data) <- gsub(".ctrl.ratio", "", names(fc.data))
fc.data <- fc.data[, colnames(ctrl.ratio_dataE)]
```

```

exprs(ctrl.ratio_dataE) <- fc.data %>%
  as.matrix() %>%
  log2()
rm(fc.data)

```

PCA - principal component analysis

```

sets <- list("raw data" = raw_dataE, "batchcl data" = batchcl_dataE, "norm data" = norm_dataE, "ctrl.ra
PCA_data <- NULL
for (i in seq_along(sets)) {
  set <- sets[[i]]
  set.name <- names(sets)[i]
  PCA_m <- t(na.omit(exprs(set)))
  if (length(PCA_m) > 50) {
    PCA <- prcomp(PCA_m, scale = FALSE)
    perc_var <-
      round(100 * PCA$sdev ^ 2 /
            sum(PCA$sdev ^ 2), 1)
    PCA_data_i <-
      data.frame(PC1 = PCA$x[, 1],
                 PC2 = PCA$x[, 2],
                 PC3 = PCA$x[, 3],
                 PC1.var = perc_var[1],
                 PC2.var = perc_var[2],
                 condition = pData(set)$condition,
                 rep = pData(set)$rep,
                 measurement = set.name)
    PCA_data <- bind_rows(PCA_data, PCA_data_i)
    rm(PCA_data_i)
  }
}
rm(i)
PCA_data$measurement <- factor(PCA_data$measurement, ordered = TRUE, levels = c("raw data", "batchcl da
ggplot(data = PCA_data, aes(PC1, PC2, colour = PC3)) +
  geom_point(aes(colour = condition, shape = rep), size = 4) +
  guides(size = "none") +
  customPlot +
  ggtitle("PCA analysis") +
  xlab("PC1") +
  ylab("PC2") +
  facet_wrap(. ~ measurement + paste("PC1:", PC1.var, "% var - PC2:", PC2.var, "% var"), scale = "free"

```

PCA analysis


```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("PCA_analysis_", script.version, ".pdf")),
        width = 14, height = 5)
write.csv(PCA_data, file = file.path(dir_save, paste0("PCA_analysis_data_", script.version, ".csv")), r
```

Merge modified data back into 'cdata'

```
cdata_i <- as.data.frame(2^exprs(batchcl_dataE))
names(cdata_i) <- paste0("batchcl_signal_sum_", names(cdata_i))
cdata_i$Gene <- rownames(cdata_i)
cdata <- left_join(cdata, cdata_i)
rm(cdata_i)

cdata_i <- as.data.frame(2^exprs(norm_dataE))
names(cdata_i) <- paste0("norm_signal_sum_", names(cdata_i))
cdata_i$Gene <- rownames(cdata_i)
cdata <- left_join(cdata, cdata_i)
rm(cdata_i)

cdata_i <- as.data.frame(2^exprs(ctrl.ratio_dataE))
names(cdata_i) <- paste0("ctrl.ratio_", names(cdata_i))
cdata_i$Gene <- rownames(cdata_i)
cdata <- left_join(cdata, cdata_i)
```

```
rm(cdata_i)
```

```
write.csv(cdata, file = file.path(dir_save, paste0("Full_dataset_", script.version, ".csv")), row.names = FALSE)
```

Create tidy data

```
mdata <- NULL
```

```
mdata_i <- tidy(raw_dataE)
mdata_i <- mdata_i %>%
  mutate(value = 2 ^ value)
names(mdata_i)[1] <- "Gene"
names(mdata_i)[2] <- "ID"
mdata_i <- left_join(mdata_i, conditions)
mdata_i$measurement <- "raw_signal_sum"
mdata <- bind_rows(mdata, mdata_i)
rm(mdata_i)
```

```
mdata_i <- tidy(batchcl_dataE)
mdata_i <- mdata_i %>%
  mutate(value = 2 ^ value)
names(mdata_i)[1] <- "Gene"
names(mdata_i)[2] <- "ID"
mdata_i <- left_join(mdata_i, conditions)
mdata_i$measurement <- "batchcl_signal_sum"
mdata <- bind_rows(mdata, mdata_i)
rm(mdata_i)
```

```
mdata_i <- tidy(norm_dataE)
mdata_i <- mdata_i %>%
  mutate(value = 2 ^ value)
names(mdata_i)[1] <- "Gene"
names(mdata_i)[2] <- "ID"
mdata_i <- left_join(mdata_i, conditions)
mdata_i$measurement <- "norm_signal_sum"
mdata <- bind_rows(mdata, mdata_i)
rm(mdata_i)
```

```
mdata_i <- tidy(ctrl.ratio_dataE)
mdata_i <- mdata_i %>%
  mutate(value = 2 ^ value)
names(mdata_i)[1] <- "Gene"
names(mdata_i)[2] <- "ID"
mdata_i <- left_join(mdata_i, conditions)
mdata_i$measurement <- "ctrl.ratio"
mdata <- bind_rows(mdata, mdata_i)
rm(mdata_i)
```

```
mdata$condition <- factor(mdata$condition, ordered = TRUE, levels = c("DMSO", "TGFb1", "TGFb1_01uM_DXM"))
mdata$measurement <- factor(mdata$measurement, ordered = TRUE, levels = c("raw_signal_sum", "batchcl_signal_sum", "norm_signal_sum", "ctrl.ratio"))
```

Data transformation overview

```
ggplot(data = subset(mdata, !grepl("ratio", measurement)), aes(condition, log2(value))) +
  geom_boxplot(aes(fill = rep)) +
  customPlot +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, hjust = 1, vjust = 0.5)) +
  facet_grid(. ~ measurement)
```



```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Normalization_overview_", script.version, ".pdf")), width = 10, height = 10)
```

```
ggplot(data = subset(mdata, grepl("ratio", measurement)), aes(condition, log2(value))) +
  geom_boxplot(aes(fill = rep)) +
  customPlot +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, hjust = 1, vjust = 0.5)) +
  facet_grid(. ~ measurement, scale = "free")
```



```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Normalization_overview_ratios_", script.version, ".pdf")), width = 6
```

LIMMA analysis

A protein is considered a 'hit', if the false discovery rate is smaller 0.05 and a fold change of at least 2-fold is observed. A protein is considered a 'candidate', if the false discovery rate is smaller 0.2 and a fold change of at least 1.5-fold is observed.

Initialize limma results data

```
limma_results <- NULL
```

Run limma analysis

```
limma_data <- norm_dataE
limma_weights <- exprs(raw_dataE)
```

```

comparison.list <- c("TGFb1 - DMSO", "TGFb1_01uM_DXM - DMSO", "TGFb1_10uM_DXM - DMSO", "DMSO_01uM_DXM -
limma_weights <- ifelse(is.na(limma_weights), 0.01, 1)
limma.cond <- factor(pData(limma_data)$condition, ordered = FALSE)
limma.rep <- factor(pData(limma_data)$rep, ordered = FALSE)
contrast.matrix <- model.matrix( ~ 0 + limma.cond + limma.rep)
colnames(contrast.matrix) <- gsub("limma.cond", "", colnames(contrast.matrix))

limma.object <- eBayes(
  contrasts.fit(
    lmFit(limma_data, design = contrast.matrix, weights = limma_weights),
    makeContrasts(contrasts = comparison.list, levels = contrast.matrix)
  )
)
for (comparison in comparison.list)
{
  limma_results_i <- limma::topTable(limma.object,
    sort.by = "t",
    coef = comparison,
    number = Inf)
  names(limma_results_i)[grep("P.Value", names(limma_results_i))] <- "pvalue.limma"
  names(limma_results_i)[grep("adj.P.Val", names(limma_results_i))] <- "fdr.limma"
  limma_results_i <- subset(limma_results_i, !is.na(logFC))
  fdr_res <- NULL
  try(fdr_res <- fdrtool(limma_results_i$t, plot = FALSE, verbose = FALSE))
  if (!is.null(fdr_res))
  {
    limma_results_i$pvalue.fdrtool <- fdr_res$pval
    limma_results_i$qval.fdrtool <- fdr_res$qval
    limma_results_i$lfd.fdrtool <- fdr_res$lfd
  }else
  {
    limma_results_i$pvalue.fdrtool <- 1
    limma_results_i$qval.fdrtool <- 1
    limma_results_i$lfd.fdrtool <- 1
  }
  limma_results_i$comparison <- comparison
  limma_results <- bind_rows(limma_results, limma_results_i)
  rm(limma_results_i, fdr_res)
}
rm(comparison.list, comparison, contrast.matrix, limma.cond, limma.rep, limma_data, limma_weights, limma

```

Fdr statistics comparison limma vs fdrtool

```

ggplot(data = limma_results, aes(abs(t))) +
  geom_line(aes(y = fdr.limma, colour = "limma - adj.P.Val")) +
  geom_line(aes(y = qval.fdrtool, colour = "fdrtool - qval")) +
  geom_point(aes(y = fdr.limma, colour = "limma - adj.P.Val")) +
  geom_point(aes(y = qval.fdrtool, colour = "fdrtool - qval")) +
  facet_wrap( ~ comparison, scale = "free_x") +
  ylab("fdr") +
  customPlot

```



```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("t_vs_fdr_limma_vs_fdrtool_", script.version, ".pdf")), width = 20, height = 15)
```

```
ggplot(data = limma_results) +
  geom_histogram(aes(pvalue.limma, alpha = 0.5, fill = "limma"), bins = 40) +
  geom_histogram(aes(pvalue.fdrtool, alpha = 0.5, fill = "fdrtool"), bins = 40) +
  guides(alpha = FALSE) +
  xlab("p-value") +
  facet_wrap(~ comparison, scale = "free_y") +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 1)) +
  customPlot
```



```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("p-value_histogram_limma_vs_fdrtool_", script.version, ".pdf")), width=
```

Hit annotation

```
limma_results$hit_annotation_method <- NA
fdr_hit_threshold <- 0.05
fdr_candidate_threshold = 0.2
fc_hit_threshold <- 2
fc_candidate_threshold <- 1.5
limma_results$pvalue <- NA
```

```

limma_results$fdr <- NA
for (comparison in unique(limma_results$comparison))
{
  limma_hits <-
    nrow(limma_results[limma_results$comparison == comparison &
      limma_results$fdr.limma <= fdr_hit_threshold, ])
  fdrtool_hits <-
    nrow(limma_results[limma_results$comparison == comparison &
      limma_results$qval.fdrtool <= fdr_hit_threshold, ])
  if (limma_hits >= fdrtool_hits)
  {
    limma_results$hit_annotation_method[limma_results$comparison == comparison] <-
      "limma"
  }
  if (fdrtool_hits > limma_hits)
  {
    limma_results$hit_annotation_method[limma_results$comparison == comparison] <-
      "fdrtool"
  }
  rm(limma_hits, fdrtool_hits)
}
rm(comparison)
table(limma_results$hit_annotation_method)

##
## fdrtool   limma
##    2226    8904

# limma_results$hit_annotation_method <- "limma"
limma_results$hit_annotation_method[!grepl("[,(,)", limma_results$comparison)] <- "limma"

limma_results$pvalue[limma_results$hit_annotation_method == "limma"] <-
  limma_results$pvalue.limma[limma_results$hit_annotation_method == "limma"]
limma_results$fdr[limma_results$hit_annotation_method == "limma"] <-
  limma_results$fdr.limma[limma_results$hit_annotation_method == "limma"]

limma_results$pvalue[limma_results$hit_annotation_method == "fdrtool"] <-
  limma_results$pvalue.fdrtool[limma_results$hit_annotation_method == "fdrtool"]
limma_results$fdr[limma_results$hit_annotation_method == "fdrtool"] <-
  limma_results$qval.fdrtool[limma_results$hit_annotation_method == "fdrtool"]

limma_results$hit <-
  with(limma_results, ifelse(fdr <= fdr_hit_threshold & abs(logFC) >=
    log2(fc_hit_threshold), TRUE, FALSE))
limma_results$hit_annotation <-
  with(limma_results,
    ifelse(fdr <= fdr_hit_threshold & abs(logFC) >=
      log2(fc_hit_threshold), "hit",
      ifelse(fdr <= fdr_candidate_threshold & abs(logFC) >=
        log2(fc_candidate_threshold), "candidate", "no hit")))
limma_results$hit_annotation <-
  factor(limma_results$hit_annotation,
    ordered = TRUE,
    levels = c("hit", "candidate", "no hit"))

```

```
with(limma_results, table(comparison, hit_annotation))
```

## comparison	hit_annotation		
	hit candidate	no hit	hit
## (DMSO_01uM_DXM - DMSO) - (TGFb1 - DMSO)	24	44	674
## (DMSO_10uM_DXM - DMSO) - (TGFb1 - DMSO)	36	63	643
## (TGFb1_01uM_DXM - DMSO) - (DMSO_01uM_DXM - DMSO)	22	25	695
## (TGFb1_01uM_DXM - DMSO) - (TGFb1 - DMSO)	0	0	742
## (TGFb1_01uM_DXM - TGFb1) - (DMSO_01uM_DXM - DMSO)	0	0	742
## (TGFb1_10uM_DXM - DMSO) - (DMSO_10uM_DXM - DMSO)	11	24	707
## (TGFb1_10uM_DXM - DMSO) - (TGFb1 - DMSO)	20	102	620
## (TGFb1_10uM_DXM - TGFb1) - (DMSO_10uM_DXM - DMSO)	0	0	742
## DMSO_01uM_DXM - DMSO	0	0	742
## DMSO_10uM_DXM - DMSO	4	43	695
## TGFb1 - DMSO	18	41	683
## TGFb1_01uM_DXM - DMSO	16	37	689
## TGFb1_01uM_DXM - TGFb1	0	0	742
## TGFb1_10uM_DXM - DMSO	36	65	641
## TGFb1_10uM_DXM - TGFb1	20	102	620

Volcano-plot

```
ggplot(data = limma_results, aes(logFC, -log10(pvalue), colour = hit_annotation)) +
  geom_vline(aes(xintercept = 0)) +
  geom_point() +
  geom_text(aes(label = gsub("[|].+", "", Gene)),
            data = subset(limma_results, hit_annotation != "no hit"),
            vjust = 0, nudge_y = 0.1, size = 2, check_overlap = TRUE) +
  facet_wrap(~ comparison + hit_annotation_method) +
  xlab("log2(fold change)") +
  customPlot
```



```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Volcano_plot_", script.version, ".pdf")), width = 20, height = 13.5)
```

MA-plot

```
ggplot(data = limma_results, aes(AveExpr, logFC, colour = hit_annotation)) +
  geom_hline(aes(yintercept = 0)) +
  geom_point() +
  geom_text(aes(label = gsub("[.]", "", Gene)),
            data = subset(limma_results, hit_annotation != "no hit"),
            vjust = 0, nudge_y = 0.1, size = 2, check_overlap = TRUE) +
```

```
facet_wrap( ~ comparison + hit_annotation_method) +
xlab("average log2(signal_sum)") +
ylab("log2(fold change)") +
customPlot
```



```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("MA_plot_", script.version, ".pdf")), width = 20, height = 13.5)
```

```
##Total.Intensity-plot
```

```
limma_results$Total.Intensity <- limma_results$average.Total.Intensity
ggplot(data = limma_results, aes(log2(Total.Intensity), logFC, colour = hit_annotation)) +
  geom_hline(aes(yintercept = 0)) +
```

```

geom_point() +
geom_text(aes(label = gsub("[.]+", "", Gene)),
          data = subset(limma_results, hit_annotation != "no hit"),
          vjust = 0, nudge_y = 0.1, size = 2, check_overlap = TRUE) +
facet_wrap(~ comparison + hit_annotation_method) +
ylab("log2(fold change)") +
customPlot

```



```

ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Total.Intensity_plot_", script.version, ".pdf")), width = 20, height

```

Fold change correlations

```
FC.correlation.list <- list(
  structure(
    c("(TGFb1_01uM_DXM - DMSO) - (DMSO_01uM_DXM - DMSO)", "TGFb1_01uM_DXM - DMSO", "DMSO_01uM_DXM - DMSO"),
    .Names = c("TGFb1_01uM_DXM_vs_DMSO_against_DMSO_01uM_DXM_vs_DMSO", "TGFb1_01uM_DXM_vs_DMSO", "DMSO_01uM_DXM_vs_DMSO"),
  ),
  structure(
    c("(TGFb1_10uM_DXM - DMSO) - (DMSO_10uM_DXM - DMSO)", "TGFb1_10uM_DXM - DMSO", "DMSO_10uM_DXM - DMSO"),
    .Names = c("TGFb1_10uM_DXM_vs_DMSO_against_DMSO_10uM_DXM_vs_DMSO", "TGFb1_10uM_DXM_vs_DMSO", "DMSO_10uM_DXM_vs_DMSO"),
  ),
  structure(
    c("(TGFb1_01uM_DXM - TGFb1) - (DMSO_01uM_DXM - DMSO)", "TGFb1_01uM_DXM - TGFb1", "DMSO_01uM_DXM - DMSO"),
    .Names = c("TGFb1_01uM_DXM_vs_TGFb1_against_DMSO_01uM_DXM_vs_DMSO", "TGFb1_01uM_DXM_vs_TGFb1", "DMSO_01uM_DXM_vs_DMSO"),
  ),
  structure(
    c("(TGFb1_10uM_DXM - TGFb1) - (DMSO_10uM_DXM - DMSO)", "TGFb1_10uM_DXM - TGFb1", "DMSO_10uM_DXM - DMSO"),
    .Names = c("TGFb1_10uM_DXM_vs_TGFb1_against_DMSO_10uM_DXM_vs_DMSO", "TGFb1_10uM_DXM_vs_TGFb1", "DMSO_10uM_DXM_vs_DMSO"),
  ),
  structure(
    c("(TGFb1_01uM_DXM - DMSO) - (TGFb1 - DMSO)", "TGFb1_01uM_DXM - DMSO", "TGFb1 - DMSO"),
    .Names = c("TGFb1_01uM_DXM_vs_DMSO_against_TGFb1_vs_DMSO", "TGFb1_01uM_DXM_vs_DMSO", "TGFb1_vs_DMSO"),
  ),
  structure(
    c("(TGFb1_10uM_DXM - DMSO) - (TGFb1 - DMSO)", "TGFb1_10uM_DXM - DMSO", "TGFb1 - DMSO"),
    .Names = c("TGFb1_10uM_DXM_vs_DMSO_against_TGFb1_vs_DMSO", "TGFb1_10uM_DXM_vs_DMSO", "TGFb1_vs_DMSO"),
  ),
  structure(
    c("(DMSO_01uM_DXM - DMSO) - (TGFb1 - DMSO)", "DMSO_01uM_DXM - DMSO", "TGFb1 - DMSO"),
    .Names = c("DMSO_01uM_DXM_vs_DMSO_against_TGFb1_vs_DMSO", "DMSO_01uM_DXM_vs_DMSO", "TGFb1_vs_DMSO"),
  ),
  structure(
    c("(DMSO_10uM_DXM - DMSO) - (TGFb1 - DMSO)", "DMSO_10uM_DXM - DMSO", "TGFb1 - DMSO"),
    .Names = c("DMSO_10uM_DXM_vs_DMSO_against_TGFb1_vs_DMSO", "DMSO_10uM_DXM_vs_DMSO", "TGFb1_vs_DMSO")
  )
)
fc.cor.data <- NULL
for (i in seq_along(FC.correlation.list))
{
  FC.correlation.list_i <- FC.correlation.list[[i]]
  fc.cor.data_x <- limma_results %>%
    group_by(Gene) %>%
    dplyr::filter(comparison == FC.correlation.list_i[3]) %>%
    mutate(x.name = names(FC.correlation.list_i)[3], x = logFC, x.hit = hit_annotation) %>%
    dplyr::select(Gene, x, x.name, x.hit)
  fc.cor.data_y <- limma_results %>%
    group_by(Gene) %>%
    dplyr::filter(comparison == FC.correlation.list_i[2]) %>%
    mutate(y.name = names(FC.correlation.list_i)[2], y = logFC, y.hit = hit_annotation) %>%
    dplyr::select(Gene, y, y.name, y.hit)
  fc.cor.data_i <- left_join(fc.cor.data_x, fc.cor.data_y)
  fc.cor.data_hit <- limma_results %>%
    group_by(Gene) %>%
    dplyr::filter(comparison == FC.correlation.list_i[1]) %>%
```

```

mutate(comparison = names(FC.correlation.list_i)[1]) %>%
  dplyr::select(Gene, comparison, hit_annotation)
fc.cor.data_i <- left_join(fc.cor.data_i, fc.cor.data_hit)
rm(fc.cor.data_x, fc.cor.data_y, fc.cor.data_hit)
fc.cor.data <- bind_rows(fc.cor.data, fc.cor.data_i)
rm(fc.cor.data_i)
}
fc.cor.data <- subset(fc.cor.data, !is.na(comparison))
fc.cor.data$hit_x_and_y <- paste(fc.cor.data$x.hit, "x -", fc.cor.data$y.hit, "y")
fc.cor.data$hit_x_and_y <- gsub("enriched ", "", fc.cor.data$hit_x_and_y)
fc.cor.data$hit_x_and_y <- factor(fc.cor.data$hit_x_and_y, ordered = TRUE,
                                levels = c("hit x - hit y",
                                           "hit x - candidate y",
                                           "candidate x - hit y",
                                           "candidate x - candidate y",
                                           "hit x - no hit y",
                                           "no hit x - hit y",
                                           "candidate x - no hit y",
                                           "no hit x - candidate y",
                                           "no hit x - no hit y"))
no.of.comparisons <- with(fc.cor.data, length(unique(paste(comparison))))
gr.width <- 4 + ceiling(sqrt(no.of.comparisons)) * 5
gr.height <- 3 + floor(sqrt(no.of.comparisons)) * 5
ggplot(data = fc.cor.data, aes(x, y, colour = hit_annotation)) +
  geom_vline(aes(xintercept = 0)) +
  geom_hline(aes(yintercept = 0)) +
  geom_abline() +
  coord_fixed(ratio = 1) +
  geom_point() +
  geom_text(aes(label = gsub("[|].+", "", Gene)),
            data = subset(fc.cor.data, hit_annotation != "no hit"),
            vjust = 0, nudge_y = 0.1, size = 2, check_overlap = TRUE) +
  facet_wrap(~ comparison + x.name + y.name, labeller = "label_both") +
  customPlot

```



```

ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Fold_change_correlation_", script.version, ".pdf")), width = gr.width)
ggplot(data = fc.cor.data, aes(x, y, colour = hit_x_and_y)) +
  geom_vline(aes(xintercept = 0)) +
  geom_hline(aes(yintercept = 0)) +
  geom_abline() +
  coord_fixed(ratio = 1) +
  geom_point() +
  geom_text(aes(label = gsub("[].+", "", Gene)),
            data = subset(fc.cor.data, x.hit %in% c("hit") | y.hit %in% c("hit")),
            vjust = 0, nudge_y = 0.1, size = 2, check_overlap = TRUE) +
  facet_wrap(~ comparison + x.name + y.name, labeller = "label_both") +

```

customPlot


```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Fold_change_correlation_alt_hit_class_", script.version, ".pdf")), w
write.csv(fc.cor.data, file = file.path(dir_save, paste0("Fold_change_correlation_data_", script.version
rm(FC.correlation.list, gr.width, gr.height)
```

Save limma results

```
write.csv(limma_results, file.path(dir_save, paste0("Limma_results_", script.version, ".csv")), row.names=NA)
```

Clustering of data

Preparation of cluster data

```
hits <- unique(subset(limma_results, hit_annotation %in% c("hit", "candidate"))$Gene)
m_clust.data <- subset(mdata, measurement == "ctrl.ratio" & Gene %in% hits) %>%
  group_by(Gene, condition) %>%
  summarise(median.value = median(value, na.rm = TRUE))
clust.data_m <- m_clust.data %>%
  mutate(key = paste(condition, sep = "_")) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  dplyr::select(Gene, key, median.value) %>%
  group_by(Gene) %>%
  spread(key = key, value = median.value) %>%
  as.data.frame()
write.csv(clust.data_m, file.path(dir_save, paste0("Clustering_data_", nrow(clust.data_m), "_proteins_")),
rownames(clust.data_m) <- clust.data_m$Gene
m_clust.data <- m_clust.data %>%
  dplyr::filter(Gene %in% clust.data_m$Gene)
clust.data_m$Gene <- NULL
clust.data_m <- clust.data_m %>%
  as.matrix() %>%
  log2()
clust.data_m[is.na(clust.data_m)] <- 0
```

PCA of clustering data

```
clust.data_PCA <- prcomp(clust.data_m, scale = FALSE)
perc_var <-
  round(100 * clust.data_PCA$sdev ^ 2 /
        sum(clust.data_PCA$sdev ^ 2), 1)
PCA_clust.data <-
  data.frame(PC1 = clust.data_PCA$x[, 1],
            PC2 = clust.data_PCA$x[, 2],
            PC3 = clust.data_PCA$x[, 3])
ggplot(data = PCA_clust.data, aes(PC1, PC2, colour = PC3)) +
  geom_point() +
  theme_bw(base_size = 12) +
  scale_colour_gradientn(colours = c("black", "#377eb8", "#984ea3",
                                     "#e41a1c", "#ff7f00", "#ffff33")) +
  ggtitle("PCA clustering data",
          subtitle = paste("PC3 - explaining", perc_var[3], "% of variability")) +
  xlab(paste("PC1 - explaining", perc_var[1], "% of variability")) +
  ylab(paste("PC2 - explaining", perc_var[2], "% of variability"))
```

PCA clustering data

PC3 – explaining 5.4 % of variability


```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("PCA_clustering_data_", script.version, ".pdf")),  
        width = 7, height = 5)  
rm(clust.data_PCA, perc_var)
```

Set number of clusters

```
cluster.number <- ceiling(sqrt(sqrt(nrow(clust.data_m)) * ncol(clust.data_m)))
```

K-means clustering

```
# plot within groups sum of squares for different cluster numbers
no <- ceiling(nrow(clust.data_m) / 4)
wss <- (no - 1) * sum(apply(clust.data_m, 2, var))
for (i in 2:(no - 1)) wss[i] <- sum(kmeans(clust.data_m,
                                         centers = i)$withinss)
plot(1:(no - 1), wss, type = "b", xlab = "number of Clusters",
     ylab = "within groups sum of squares")
abline(v = cluster.number, col = "red")
```



```
kmeans.fit <- kmeans(clust.data_m, cluster.number)
cluster.groups <- data.frame(Gene = names(kmeans.fit$cluster),
                             kmeans.cluster.group = kmeans.fit$cluster)
rm(wss, kmeans.fit, no)
```

Hierarchical clustering

```
d <- dist(clust.data_m, method = "euclidean")
hclust.fit <- hclust(d, method = "ward.D2")
cluster.groups_hclust <-
  data.frame(Gene = names(cutree(hclust.fit, k = cluster.number)),
             hclust.cluster.group = cutree(hclust.fit, k = cluster.number))
cluster.groups <- left_join(cluster.groups, cluster.groups_hclust)
rm(cluster.groups_hclust)
m_clust.data <- left_join(m_clust.data, cluster.groups)
```

```
m_clust.data$Gene <- factor(m_clust.data$Gene, ordered = TRUE,  
                           levels = hclust.fit$labels[hclust.fit$order])  
rm(d, hclust.fit)
```

Plot clustering results

```
gr.width <- 2.5 + ncol(clust.data_m) * 0.1 + max(nchar(rownames(clust.data_m))) * 0.008  
gr.height <- 2.5 + nrow(clust.data_m) * 0.01  
ggplot(data = m_clust.data, aes(condition, Gene)) +  
  geom_tile(aes(fill = log2(median.value))) +  
  scale_fill_gradient2(low = "#2166ac", high = "#b2182b", midpoint = 0,  
                      mid = "#f7f7f7", name = "log2.ratio") +  
  theme_bw(base_size = 12) +  
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, hjust = 1, vjust = 0.5),  
        axis.text.y = element_text(size = 1)) +  
  ylab("gene")
```



```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Heatmap_hits_", nrow(clust.data_m), "_proteins_", script.version, ".pdf"))
```

```
# Clustering heatmaps
ggplot(data = cluster.groups, aes(hclust.cluster.group, kmeans.cluster.group)) +
  geom_abline(colour = "grey") +
  geom_jitter(width = 0.2, height = 0.2, alpha = 0.3) +
  scale_x_continuous(breaks = 1:cluster.number) +
  scale_y_continuous(breaks = 1:cluster.number) +
  customPlot +
  theme(panel.grid.minor = element_blank())
```



```

# PCA with cluster results
m_cluster.groups <- cluster.groups %>%
  group_by(Gene) %>%
  gather(-Gene, key = "cluster.group", value = "cluster") %>%
  mutate(cluster.group = gsub(".cluster.group", "", cluster.group))
PCA_clust.data$Gene <- rownames(PCA_clust.data)
PCA_clust.data <- left_join(PCA_clust.data, m_cluster.groups)
PCA_clust.data$cluster <- factor(PCA_clust.data$cluster)
ggplot(data = PCA_clust.data, aes(PC1, PC2, colour = cluster)) +
  geom_point() +
  theme_bw(base_size = 12) +

```

```
facet_wrap(~ cluster.group) +
geom_text(aes(label = Gene), size = 0.2, colour = "black")
```



```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("PCA_clustering_data_", cluster.number, "_cluster_", nrow(clust.data_m),
width = 10, height = 5)
gr.height <- 2.5 + nrow(clust.data_m) * 0.01 + cluster.number * 0.1
ggplot(data = m_clust.data, aes(condition, Gene)) +
  geom_tile(aes(fill = log2(median.value))) +
  scale_fill_gradient2(low = "#2166ac", high = "#b2182b", midpoint = 0,
mid = "#f7f7f7", name = "log2.ratio") +
  facet_grid(hclust.cluster.group ~ ., scale = "free", space = "free") +
```

```

theme_bw(base_size = 12) +
theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, hjust = 1, vjust = 0.5),
      axis.text.y = element_text(size = 1)) +
ylab("gene") +
ggtitle("hierarchical clustering")

```



```

ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Clustering_heatmap_hits_hclust_", cluster.number, "_cluster_", row(
width = gr.width, height = gr.height)

```

```

ggplot(data = m_clust.data, aes(condition, Gene)) +
geom_tile(aes(fill = log2(median.value))) +

```

```

scale_fill_gradient2(low = "#2166ac", high = "#b2182b", midpoint = 0,
                    mid = "#f7f7f7", name = "log2.ratio") +
facet_grid(kmeans.cluster.group ~ ., scale = "free", space = "free") +
theme_bw(base_size = 12) +
theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, hjust = 1, vjust = 0.5),
      axis.text.y = element_text(size = 1)) +
ylab("gene") +
ggtitle("kmeans clustering")

```



```

ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Clustering_heatmap_hits_kmeans_", cluster.number, "_cluster_", row(
width = gr.width, height = gr.height)

```

```

# Line plots
gr.width <- 4 + ceiling(sqrt(cluster.number)) * 3
gr.height <- 2.5 + floor(sqrt(cluster.number)) * 3
ggplot(data = m_clust.data, aes(condition, log2(median.value))) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0) +
  geom_line(aes(group = paste(Gene, hclust.cluster.group)), alpha = 0.1) +
  geom_smooth(fun.data = "mean_se", stat = "summary", aes(group = paste(hclust.cluster.group))) +
  facet_wrap(~ hclust.cluster.group) +
  customPlot +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, hjust = 1, vjust = 0.5)) +
  ggtitle("hierarchical clustering") +
  ylab("log2(ratio)")

```

hierarchical clustering


```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Clustering_line_plot_hclust_", cluster.number, "_cluster_", row(cluster.number,
width = gr.width, height = gr.height))
```

```
ggplot(data = m_clust.data, aes(condition, log2(median.value))) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0) +
  geom_line(aes(group = paste(Gene, kmeans.cluster.group)), alpha = 0.1) +
  geom_smooth(fun.data = "mean_se", stat = "summary", aes(group = paste(kmeans.cluster.group))) +
  facet_wrap(~ kmeans.cluster.group) +
  customPlot +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, hjust = 1, vjust = 0.5)) +
  ggtitle("kmeans clustering") +
```

```
ylab("log2(ratio)")
```

kmeans clustering


```
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Clustering_line_plot_kmeans_", cluster.number, "_cluster_", row(cluster.groups, width = gr.width, height = gr.height))  
write.csv(cluster.groups, file.path(dir_save, paste0("Cluster_results_", cluster.number, "cluster_", row(cluster.groups, width = gr.width, height = gr.height))
```

Save R workspace

```
save.image(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Workspace_", script.version, ".RData")))
# load(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Workspace_", script.version, ".RData")))
```

Comparative GO term enrichment analysis

Preparation

```
library(clusterProfiler)
library(org.Hs.eg.db)
calculateFE <- function(GeneRatio, BgRatio)
{
  GeneRatio <- as.numeric(unlist(str_split(GeneRatio, pattern = "/")))
  BgRatio <- as.numeric(unlist(str_split(BgRatio, pattern = "/")))
  odds_ratio <- (GeneRatio[1] / GeneRatio[2]) / (BgRatio[1] / BgRatio[2])
  return(odds_ratio)
}
ID_LUT <- bitr(geneID = cdata$Gene, fromType = "SYMBOL", toType = "ENTREZID", OrgDb = org.Hs.eg.db)
names(ID_LUT) <- c("Gene", "ENTREZID")
```

GO analysis for hits of differential abundance analysis

```
limma_results <- left_join(limma_results, ID_LUT)
ego_data <- limma_results %>%
  dplyr::filter(!is.na(ENTREZID), hit_annotation %in% c("hit", "candidate")) %>%
  dplyr::select(ENTREZID, comparison, logFC) %>%
  unique() %>%
  mutate(direction = ifelse(logFC > 0, "upregulated", "downregulated")) %>%
  mutate(comparison = gsub("[.]", "_", comparison))
```

Cellular compartment

```
ego_results_DE_CC <- NULL
try(ego_results_DE_CC <- compareCluster(ENTREZID ~ comparison + direction,
                                       data = ego_data, fun = "enrichGO",
                                       OrgDb = org.Hs.eg.db,
                                       keyType = "ENTREZID",
                                       ont = "CC",
                                       readable = TRUE))
#universe = ID_LUT$ENTREZID))

if (!is.null(ego_results_DE_CC))
{
  ego_results_DE_CC_table <- ego_results_DE_CC@compareClusterResult
  ego_results_DE_CC_table <- ego_results_DE_CC_table %>%
    group_by(ID, comparison, direction) %>%
    mutate(odds_ratio = calculateFE(GeneRatio, BgRatio))
  ego_results_DE_CC_table$Description <- factor(ego_results_DE_CC_table$Description, levels = unique(ego_results_DE_CC_table$Description))
  write.csv(ego_results_DE_CC_table, file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_DE_CC_limma_results_", script.version, ".csv")))
  ego_sub <- ego_results_DE_CC_table %>%
    group_by(comparison, direction) %>%
    slice_head(n = 10)
```



```

ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_DE_MF_cnetplot_limma_results_", script.version, ".pdf",
width = 15, height = 15)
}

```

Biological process

```

ego_results_DE_BP <- NULL
try(ego_results_DE_BP <- compareCluster(ENTREZID ~ comparison + direction,
data = ego_data, fun = "enrichGO",
OrgDb = org.Hs.eg.db,
keyType = "ENTREZID",
ont = "BP",
readable = TRUE))
#universe = ID_LUT$ENTREZID))

if (!is.null(ego_results_DE_BP))
{
ego_results_DE_BP_table <- ego_results_DE_BP@compareClusterResult
ego_results_DE_BP_table <- ego_results_DE_BP_table %>%
group_by(ID, comparison, direction) %>%
mutate(odds_ratio = calculateFE(GeneRatio, BgRatio))
ego_results_DE_BP_table$Description <- factor(ego_results_DE_BP_table$Description, levels = unique(ego_results_DE_BP_table$Description))
write.csv(ego_results_DE_BP_table, file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_DE_BP_limma_results_", script.version, ".csv")))
ego_sub <- ego_results_DE_BP_table %>%
group_by(comparison, direction) %>%
slice_head(n = 10)
ggplot(data = ego_sub, aes(paste(comparison, direction), Description)) +
geom_point(aes(size = odds_ratio, colour = -log10(p.adjust))) +
theme_bw(base_size = 12) +
scale_colour_gradientn(colours = c("#377eb8", "#984ea3", "#e41a1c", "#ff7f00", "#ffff33")) +
ggtitle("Biological process") +
ylab("") +
xlab("") +
theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, vjust = 0.5, hjust = 1))
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_DE_BP_dotplot_limma_results_", script.version, ".pdf",
width = max(nchar(as.character(ego_sub$Description))) * 0.06 + with(ego_sub, length(unique(paste(comparison, direction)))) * 0.06,
height = length(unique(ego_sub$Description)) * 0.12 + max(with(ego_sub, nchar(unique(paste(comparison, direction)))) * 0.12,
cnetplot(ego_results_DE_BP, showCategory = 5) +
ggtitle("Biological process") +
theme_bw(base_size = 12)
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_DE_BP_cnetplot_limma_results_", script.version, ".pdf",
width = 15, height = 15)
}

```

GO analysis for clustering results

```

cluster.groups <- left_join(cluster.groups, ID_LUT)

```

Cellular compartment

```

ego_results_clustering_CC <- NULL
try(ego_results_clustering_CC <- compareCluster(ENTREZID ~ kmeans.cluster.group,
data = cluster.groups, fun = "enrichGO",

```

```

                                OrgDb = org.Hs.eg.db,
                                keyType = "ENTREZID",
                                ont = "CC",
                                readable = TRUE))
                                #universe = ID_LUT$ENTREZID))
if (!is.null(ego_results_clustering_CC))
{
ego_results_clustering_CC_table <- ego_results_clustering_CC@compareClusterResult
ego_results_clustering_CC_table <- ego_results_clustering_CC_table %>%
  group_by(ID, kmeans.cluster.group) %>%
  mutate(odds_ratio = calculateFE(GeneRatio, BgRatio))
ego_results_clustering_CC_table$Description <- factor(ego_results_clustering_CC_table$Description, levels = unique(ego_results_clustering_CC_table$Description))
write.csv(ego_results_clustering_CC_table, file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_cluster_CC_kmeans_clustering_", script.version, ".csv")))
ego_sub <- ego_results_clustering_CC_table %>%
  group_by(kmeans.cluster.group) %>%
  slice_head(n = 10)
ggplot(data = ego_sub, aes(kmeans.cluster.group, Description)) +
  geom_point(aes(size = odds_ratio, colour = -log10(p.adjust))) +
  theme_bw(base_size = 12) +
  scale_colour_gradientn(colours = c("#377eb8", "#984ea3", "#e41a1c", "#ff7f00", "#ffff33")) +
  ggtitle("Cellular compartment") +
  ylab("")
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_cluster_CC_dotplot_kmeans_clustering_", script.version, ".pdf")),
        width = max(nchar(as.character(ego_sub$Description))) * 0.06 + length(unique(ego_sub$kmeans.cluster.group)) * 0.06, 10),
        height = length(unique(ego_sub$Description)) * 0.12 + 4)
cnetplot(ego_results_clustering_CC, showCategory = 5) +
  ggtitle("Cellular compartment") +
  theme_bw(base_size = 12)
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_cluster_CC_cnetplot_kmeans_clustering_", script.version, ".pdf")),
        width = 15, height = 15)
}

```

Molecular function

```

ego_results_clustering_MF <- NULL
try(ego_results_clustering_MF <- compareCluster(ENTREZID ~ kmeans.cluster.group,
                                data = cluster.groups, fun = "enrichGO",
                                OrgDb = org.Hs.eg.db,
                                keyType = "ENTREZID",
                                ont = "MF",
                                readable = TRUE))
                                #universe = ID_LUT$ENTREZID))
if (!is.null(ego_results_clustering_MF))
{
ego_results_clustering_MF_table <- ego_results_clustering_MF@compareClusterResult
ego_results_clustering_MF_table <- ego_results_clustering_MF_table %>%
  group_by(ID, kmeans.cluster.group) %>%
  mutate(odds_ratio = calculateFE(GeneRatio, BgRatio))
ego_results_clustering_MF_table$Description <- factor(ego_results_clustering_MF_table$Description, levels = unique(ego_results_clustering_MF_table$Description))
write.csv(ego_results_clustering_MF_table, file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_cluster_MF_kmeans_clustering_", script.version, ".csv")))
ego_sub <- ego_results_clustering_MF_table %>%
  group_by(kmeans.cluster.group) %>%
  slice_head(n = 10)

```

```

ggplot(data = ego_sub, aes(kmeans.cluster.group, Description)) +
  geom_point(aes(size = odds_ratio, colour = -log10(p.adjust))) +
  theme_bw(base_size = 12) +
  scale_colour_gradientn(colours = c("#377eb8", "#984ea3", "#e41a1c", "#ff7f00", "#ffff33")) +
  ggtitle("Molecular function") +
  ylab("")
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_cluster_MF_dotplot_kmeans_clustering_", script.version,
  width = max(nchar(as.character(ego_sub$Description))) * 0.06 + length(unique(ego_sub$kmeans.cluster.group)) * 0.06 + length(unique(ego_sub$Description)) * 0.12 + 4)
  height = length(unique(ego_sub$Description)) * 0.12 + 4)
cnetplot(ego_results_clustering_MF, showCategory = 5) +
  ggtitle("Molecular function") +
  theme_bw(base_size = 12)
ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_cluster_MF_cnetplot_kmeans_clustering_", script.version,
  width = 15, height = 15)
}

```

Biological process

```

ego_results_clustering_BP <- NULL
try(ego_results_clustering_BP <- compareCluster(ENTREZID ~ kmeans.cluster.group,
  data = cluster.groups, fun = "enrichGO",
  OrgDb = org.Hs.eg.db,
  keyType = "ENTREZID",
  ont = "BP",
  readable = TRUE))
#universe = ID_LUT$ENTREZID))
if (!is.null(ego_results_clustering_BP))
{
  ego_results_clustering_BP_table <- ego_results_clustering_BP@compareClusterResult
  ego_results_clustering_BP_table <- ego_results_clustering_BP_table %>%
    group_by(ID, kmeans.cluster.group) %>%
    mutate(odds_ratio = calculateFE(GeneRatio, BgRatio))
  ego_results_clustering_BP_table$Description <- factor(ego_results_clustering_BP_table$Description, levels = unique(ego_results_clustering_BP_table$Description))
  write.csv(ego_results_clustering_BP_table, file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_cluster_BP_kmeans_clustering_", script.version,
  ego_sub <- ego_results_clustering_BP_table %>%
    group_by(kmeans.cluster.group) %>%
    slice_head(n = 10)
  ggplot(data = ego_sub, aes(kmeans.cluster.group, Description)) +
    geom_point(aes(size = odds_ratio, colour = -log10(p.adjust))) +
    theme_bw(base_size = 12) +
    scale_colour_gradientn(colours = c("#377eb8", "#984ea3", "#e41a1c", "#ff7f00", "#ffff33")) +
    ggtitle("Biological process") +
    ylab("")
  ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_cluster_BP_dotplot_kmeans_clustering_", script.version,
    width = max(nchar(as.character(ego_sub$Description))) * 0.06 + length(unique(ego_sub$kmeans.cluster.group)) * 0.06 + length(unique(ego_sub$Description)) * 0.12 + 4)
    height = length(unique(ego_sub$Description)) * 0.12 + 4)
  cnetplot(ego_results_clustering_BP, showCategory = 5) +
    ggtitle("Biological process") +
    theme_bw(base_size = 12)
  ggsave(file.path(dir_save, paste0("GO_enrichment_cluster_BP_cnetplot_kmeans_clustering_", script.version,
    width = 15, height = 15)
}

```

Save R workspace

```
save.image(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Workspace_", script.version, ".RData")))
# load(file.path(dir_save, paste0("Workspace_", script.version, ".RData")))
```

Save Session information

```
sessionInfo()
```

```
## R version 4.0.4 (2021-02-15)
## Platform: x86_64-w64-mingw32/x64 (64-bit)
## Running under: Windows 10 x64 (build 19045)
##
## Matrix products: default
##
## locale:
## [1] LC_COLLATE=English_United States.1252
## [2] LC_CTYPE=English_United States.1252
## [3] LC_MONETARY=English_United States.1252
## [4] LC_NUMERIC=C
## [5] LC_TIME=English_United States.1252
##
## attached base packages:
## [1] stats4      parallel  stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets
## [8] methods    base
##
## other attached packages:
## [1] org.Hs.eg.db_3.12.0      AnnotationDbi_1.52.0    IRanges_2.24.1
## [4] clusterProfiler_3.18.1  forcats_0.5.1          stringr_1.4.0
## [7] dplyr_1.0.4             purrr_0.3.4            readr_1.4.0
## [10] tidyr_1.1.2            tibble_3.0.6           ggplot2_3.3.3
## [13] tidyverse_1.3.0        biobroom_1.22.0        broom_0.7.5
## [16] fdrtool_1.2.16         gplots_3.1.1           MSnbase_2.15.7
## [19] ProtGenerics_1.22.0    S4Vectors_0.28.1      mzR_2.24.1
## [22] Rcpp_1.0.8.3           limma_3.46.0           vsn_3.58.0
## [25] Biobase_2.50.0         BiocGenerics_0.36.0
##
## loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
## [1] fgsea_1.16.0            colorspace_2.0-0       ellipsis_0.3.1
## [4] qvalue_2.22.0          fs_1.5.0               rstudioapi_0.13
## [7] farver_2.0.3           hexbin_1.28.2         graphlayouts_0.7.1
## [10] affyio_1.60.0          ggrepel_0.9.1         bit64_4.0.5
## [13] scatterpie_0.1.5      fansi_0.4.2           lubridate_1.7.9.2
## [16] xml2_1.3.2            splines_4.0.4         codetools_0.2-18
## [19] ncd4_1.17             doParallel_1.0.16     cachem_1.0.3
## [22] GOSemSim_2.16.1       impute_1.64.0         knitr_1.31
## [25] polyclip_1.10-0       jsonlite_1.7.2        GO.db_3.12.1
## [28] dbplyr_2.1.0          ggforce_0.3.2         BiocManager_1.30.10
## [31] compiler_4.0.4        httr_1.4.2            rvcheck_0.1.8
## [34] backports_1.2.1       Matrix_1.3-2          assertthat_0.2.1
## [37] fastmap_1.1.0         cli_2.3.1              tweenr_1.0.1
## [40] htmltools_0.5.2      tools_4.0.4           igraph_1.2.6
## [43] gtable_0.3.0         glue_1.4.2            affy_1.68.0
```

```

## [46] reshape2_1.4.4      DO.db_2.9           enrichplot_1.10.2
## [49] fastmatch_1.1-0      MALDIquant_1.19.3  cellranger_1.1.0
## [52] vctrs_0.3.6         preprocessCore_1.52.1 iterators_1.0.13
## [55] ggraph_2.0.4        xfun_0.30          rvest_0.3.6
## [58] lifecycle_1.0.0     gtools_3.8.2       XML_3.99-0.5
## [61] DOSE_3.16.0         zlibbioc_1.36.0    MASS_7.3-53.1
## [64] scales_1.1.1        tidygraph_1.2.0    pcaMethods_1.82.0
## [67] hms_1.0.0           RColorBrewer_1.1-2 yaml_2.2.1
## [70] memoise_2.0.0       gridExtra_2.3      downloader_0.4
## [73] stringi_1.5.3       RSQlite_2.2.3      highr_0.8
## [76] foreach_1.5.1       caTools_1.18.1     BiocParallel_1.24.1
## [79] rlang_0.4.10        pkgconfig_2.0.3    bitops_1.0-6
## [82] mzID_1.28.0         evaluate_0.18       lattice_0.20-41
## [85] labeling_0.4.2      shadowtext_0.0.7   cowplot_1.1.1
## [88] bit_4.0.4           tidyselect_1.1.0   plyr_1.8.6
## [91] magrittr_2.0.1      R6_2.5.0           generics_0.1.0
## [94] DBI_1.1.1           pillar_1.5.0       haven_2.3.1
## [97] withr_2.4.1         modelr_0.1.8       crayon_1.4.1
## [100] KernSmooth_2.23-18 utf8_1.1.4         rmarkdown_2.14
## [103] viridis_0.5.1       grid_4.0.4         readxl_1.3.1
## [106] data.table_1.13.6   blob_1.2.1         reprex_1.0.0
## [109] digest_0.6.27       munsell_0.5.0      viridisLite_0.3.0

```

Plot individual proteins

```

f.name <- file.path(dir_save, paste0("all_proteins_", script.version, ".pdf"))
pdf(width = 6, height = 14, file = f.name)
genes <- unique(cdata$Gene)
genes <- sort(genes)
pb <- txtProgressBar(min = 0, max = length(genes), style = 3)
for (i in seq_along(genes))
{
  gene <- genes[i]
  setTxtProgressBar(pb, i)
  mdata_i <- subset(mdata, Gene == gene)
  cdata_i <- subset(cdata, Gene == gene)
  if (nrow(cdata_i) == 1 & nrow(mdata_i) > 0)
  {
    titlestring <- paste(cdata_i$Gene[1], "-", cdata_i$Protein.ID[1])
    try(
      print(
        ggplot(data = mdata_i, aes(condition, log2(value), fill = condition)) +
          geom_boxplot() +
          geom_point(aes(shape = rep)) +
          facet_grid(measurement ~ ., space = "free_x", scale = "free") +
          customPlot +
          theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, hjust = 1, vjust = 0.5)) +
          ggtitle(titlestring, subtitle = cdata_i$Protein.Description[1])
      )
    )
    rm(titlestring)
  }
  rm(mdata_i, cdata_i)
}

```

```

}
dev.off()
close(pb)

f.name <- file.path(dir_save, paste0("hit_proteins_", script.version, ".pdf"))
pdf(width = 6, height = 14, file = f.name)
genes <- unique(subset(limma_results, hit_annotation %in% c("hit", "candidate"))$Gene)
genes <- sort(genes)
pb <- txtProgressBar(min = 0, max = length(genes), style = 3)
for (i in seq_along(genes))
{
  gene <- genes[i]
  setTxtProgressBar(pb, i)
  mdata_i <- subset(mdata, Gene == gene)
  cdata_i <- subset(cdata, Gene == gene)
  if (nrow(cdata_i) == 1 & nrow(mdata_i) > 0)
  {
    titlestring <- paste(cdata_i$Gene[1], "-", cdata_i$Protein.ID[1])
    try(
      print(
        ggplot(data = mdata_i, aes(condition, log2(value), fill = condition)) +
          geom_boxplot() +
          geom_point(aes(shape = rep)) +
          facet_grid(measurement ~ ., space = "free_x", scale = "free") +
          customPlot +
          theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, hjust = 1, vjust = 0.5)) +
          ggtitle(titlestring, subtitle = cdata_i$Protein.Description[1])
      )
    )
    rm(titlestring)
  }
  rm(mdata_i, cdata_i)
}
dev.off()
close(pb)

```